

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 45:0 For the choir director; according to the [†]Shoshannim. A [°]Maskil of the sons of Korah. A Song of Love.</p>	<p>Psa. 45:1 לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־שְׁשָׁנִים לְבָנֵי־קִרַח מִשְׁכִּיל נְשִׁיר</p>
<p>Psa. 45:1 My heart ¹overflows with a good theme; I ²address my ³verses to the ⁴King; My tongue is the pen of ^aa ready writer. ² You are fairer than the sons of men; ^aGrace is poured ¹upon Your lips; Therefore God has ^bblessed You forever.</p>	<p>יְדִידָתָּ : ² רָחַשׁ לְבָבִי דְּבַר טוֹב אָמַר אָנֹכִי מִעֲשֵׂי לְמַלְךְ לְשׁוֹנֵי עֵט סוּפֵר מִהָיֹר : ³ יַפְיֹפִיתָ מִבְּנֵי אָדָם תְּהוֹצֵק חַן בְּשִׁפְתוֹתֶיךָ עַל־כֵּן בֵּרַכְךָ אֱלֹהִים לְעוֹלָם : ⁴ תִּגְדֹר־תִּרְבֶּךָ עַל־יָרְךָ גְּבוּרַת הַיְדֹרֶךָ וַתִּדְרֹךְ : ⁵ וַתִּדְרֹךְ צִלְחַת רָכַב עַל־דְּבַר־אַמָּת וַעֲנָוָה־צָדֵק וַתֹּרֶךְ נֹרְאוֹת יִמִּינֶךָ : ⁶ תִּצְיֹךְ שְׁשׁוֹנִים עַמִּים תַּחֲתֶיךָ יִפְּלוּ בְּלֵב אוֹיְבֵי הַמֶּלֶךְ : כִּסְאֶךָ אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם ⁷ וְעַד שִׁבְט מִיֶּשֶׁר שִׁבְט מִלְכוּתֶךָ : ⁸ אֶתְהַבֵּת צָדֵק</p>
<p>Psa. 45:3 Gird ^aYour sword on <i>Your</i> thigh, O ^{1b}Mighty One, <i>In</i> Your splendor and Your majesty! ⁴ And in Your majesty ride on victoriously, For the cause of truth and ^ameekness <i>and</i> righteousness; Let Your ^bright hand teach You ¹awesome things. ⁵ Your ^aarrows are sharp; The ^bpeoples fall under You; <i>Your arrows are</i> ^cin the heart of the King's enemies.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־שְׁשָׁנִים לְבָנֵי־קִרַח מִשְׁכִּיל נְשִׁיר יְדִידָתָּ : ² רָחַשׁ לְבָבִי דְּבַר טוֹב אָמַר אָנֹכִי מִעֲשֵׂי לְמַלְךְ לְשׁוֹנֵי עֵט סוּפֵר מִהָיֹר : ³ יַפְיֹפִיתָ מִבְּנֵי אָדָם תְּהוֹצֵק חַן בְּשִׁפְתוֹתֶיךָ עַל־כֵּן בֵּרַכְךָ אֱלֹהִים לְעוֹלָם : ⁴ תִּגְדֹר־תִּרְבֶּךָ עַל־יָרְךָ גְּבוּרַת הַיְדֹרֶךָ וַתִּדְרֹךְ : ⁵ וַתִּדְרֹךְ צִלְחַת רָכַב עַל־דְּבַר־אַמָּת וַעֲנָוָה־צָדֵק וַתֹּרֶךְ נֹרְאוֹת יִמִּינֶךָ : ⁶ תִּצְיֹךְ שְׁשׁוֹנִים עַמִּים תַּחֲתֶיךָ יִפְּלוּ בְּלֵב אוֹיְבֵי הַמֶּלֶךְ : כִּסְאֶךָ אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם ⁷ וְעַד שִׁבְט מִיֶּשֶׁר שִׁבְט מִלְכוּתֶךָ : ⁸ אֶתְהַבֵּת צָדֵק</p>
<p>Psa. 45:6 ^aYour throne, O God, is forever and ever; A scepter of ^buprightness is the scepter of Your kingdom. ⁷ You have ^aloved righteousness and hated wickedness;</p>	<p>כִּסְאֶךָ אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם ⁷ וְעַד שִׁבְט מִיֶּשֶׁר שִׁבְט מִלְכוּתֶךָ : ⁸ אֶתְהַבֵּת צָדֵק</p>

Therefore God, Your God, has
^banointed You

With the oil of joy above Your
fellows.

⁸ All Your garments are *fragrant with*
"myrrh and aloes and cassia;

Out of ivory palaces ^bstringed
instruments have made You glad.

⁹ Kings' daughters are among *"Your*
noble ladies;

At Your ^bright hand stands the
queen in *'gold from Ophir.*

Psa. 45:10 Listen, O daughter, give
attention and incline your ear:

"Forget your people and your
father's house;

¹¹ Then the King will desire your
beauty.

Because He is your *"Lord, ^bbow*
down to Him.

¹² The daughter of *"Tyre will come*
with a gift;

The ^brich among the people will
seek your favor.

Psa. 45:13 The King's daughter is all
glorious within;

Her clothing is *"interwoven with*
gold.

¹⁴ She will be *"led to the King ^bin*
embroidered work;

The *'virgins, her companions who*
follow her,

Will be brought to You.

¹⁵ They will be led forth with
gladness and rejoicing;

They will enter into the King's
palace.

וּתְשַׁנָּא רִשְׁעַ עַל-כֵּן |

מִשְׁחָךְ אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהֶיךָ

שָׁמֶן שָׁשׂוֹן מִחֲבֵרֶיךָ : ⁹

מִרְוָאֵהָלוֹת קָצִיעוֹת כָּל-

בְּגָדֶיךָ מִן-הַיְכָלִי שֵׁן

מִנִּי שִׁמְחֹהךָ : ¹⁰ בְּנֹת

מַלְכִים בִּיִּקְרוּתֶיךָ נִצְבָּה

שִׁגְלָ לַיְמִינֶךָ בְּכַתֶּם

אוֹפִיר : ¹¹ שְׁמַעִי-בַת וְרֵאֵי

וְהִטִּי אָזְנֶךָ וְשִׁכְחִי עַמֶּךָ

וּבֵית אָבִיךָ : ¹² וְיִתְאַוּ

הַמֶּלֶךְ יִפְיֶיךָ כִּי-הוּא

אֲדֹנֶיךָ וְהִשְׁתַּחֲוֶי-לוֹ : ¹³

וּבַת-צָר אֲבַמְנַחָה פָּנֶיךָ

יִתְלוּ עַשְׂרֵי עָם : ¹⁴ כָּל-

כְּבוֹדָה בַת-מֶלֶךְ פְּנִימָה

מִמִּשְׁבְּצוֹת זָהָב לְבוּשָׁה :

¹⁵ לְרִקְמוֹת תוֹבֵל לְמֶלֶךְ

בְּתוֹלוֹת אֲחֵרֶיהָ רַעוּתֶיהָ

מוֹבְאוֹת לָךְ : ¹⁶ תוֹבֵלָנָה

בְּשִׁמְחַת וְגִיל תְּבֹאִינָה

Psa. 45:16 In place of your fathers will be your sons;

You shall make them princes in all the earth.

¹⁷ I will cause "Your name to be remembered in all generations;

Therefore the peoples ^bwill give You thanks forever and ever.

בְּהִיכַל מְלֹךְ : ¹⁷ תַּחַת
אֲבֹתֶיךָ יִהְיוּ בְּנֶיךָ
תִּשְׁתַּמְּחוּ לְשָׂרִים בְּכָל-
הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁸ אֲזַכֶּרְהָ שִׁמְךָ
בְּכָל-יָד וָדָר עַל-כֵּן
עַמִּים יִהְיוּךָ לְעַלְמֵם וָעַד :

References

<p>Psalm 45:1 ¹Lit <i>is astir</i> ²Lit <i>am saying</i> ³Lit <i>works</i> ⁴Probably refers to Solomon as a type of Christ ^aEzra 7:6</p> <p>Psalm 45:2 ¹Or <i>through</i> ^aLuke 4:22 ^bPs 21:6</p> <p>Psalm 45:3 ¹Or <i>warrior</i> ^aHeb 4:12; Rev 1:16 ^bIs 9:6</p> <p>Psalm 45:4 ¹Or <i>fearful</i> ^aZeph 2:3 ^bPs 21:8</p> <p>Psalm 45:5 ^aPs 18:14; 120:4; Is 5:28; 7:13 ^bPs 92:9 ^c2 Sam 18:14</p> <p>Psalm 45:6 ^aPs 93:2; Heb 1:8, 9 ^bPs 98:9</p> <p>Psalm 45:7 ^aPs 11:7; 33:5 ^bPs 2:2</p>	<p>Psalm 45:8 ^aSong 4:14; John 19:39 ^bPs 150:4</p> <p>Psalm 45:9 ^aSong 6:8 ^b1 Kin 2:19 ^c1 Kin 9:28; Is 13:12</p> <p>Psalm 45:10 ^aDeut 21:13; Ruth 1:16, 17</p> <p>Psalm 45:11 ^aGen 18:12; 1 Pet 3:6 ^bEph 5:33</p> <p>Psalm 45:12 ^aPs 87:4 ^bPs 22:29; 68:29; 72:10, 11; Is 49:23</p> <p>Psalm 45:13 ^aEx 39:2, 3</p> <p>Psalm 45:14 ^aSong 1:4 ^bJudg 5:30; Ezek 16:10 ^cPs 45:9</p> <p>Psalm 45:17 ^aMal 1:11 ^bPs 138:4</p>
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Targum

Psa. 45:1 For praise; concerning those who sit in the Sanhedrin of Moses, which was spoken in prophecy by the sons of Korah; a good lesson, and a psalm, and a thanksgiving. ² My heart desires fine speech; I will speak my work to the king; the utterance of my tongue is quick, like the pen of a fluent scribe. ³ Your beauty, O King Messiah, is greater than the sons of men; the spirit of prophecy has been placed on your lips; because of this the LORD has blessed you forever. ⁴ Gird your sword on your thigh, O champion; your glory and your brilliance is to kill kings as well as rulers. ⁵ And your brilliance is great; therefore you will succeed in mounting the horse of the kingdom, by reason of faithfulness and truth and humility and righteousness; and the LORD will teach you to do fearful things with your right hand. ⁶ Your arrows are drawn to kill Gentile hordes; beneath you they will fall; and the sons of your bow will be released into the heart of the enemies of the king. ⁷ The throne of your glory, O LORD, lasts forever and ever; the scepter of your kingdom is an upright scepter. ⁸ Because you have loved righteousness and hated wickedness – because of this the LORD your God has anointed you with the oil of gladness more than your fellows. ⁹ Pure myrrh and aloe-wood and cassia – your garments are perfected, from the palaces paved with ivory below; from me they will make you glad. ¹⁰ The provinces of the kingdom come to welcome you and to honor you, while the book of Torah is stationed at your right side, and written in gold from Ophir. ¹¹ Hear, O congregation of Israel, the Torah of his mouth, and see the wonders of his deeds, and incline your ear to the words of Torah, and you will forget the evil deeds of the wicked of your people, and the place of idols that you worshipped in the house of your father. ¹² And then the king will desire your beauty; for he is your master and you will bow down to him. ¹³ And those who dwell in the fortress of Tyre will come with an offering, and the rich Gentiles will seek your face at your sanctuary. ¹⁴ All the best and choicest sacrifices from the provinces, the treasuries of the kings that are hidden within, will they bring for the priests whose clothing is chased with pure gold. ¹⁵ In their decorated garments they will offer their sacrifices before the king of the world, and the rest of their fellows who are scattered among the Gentiles will be brought in joy to you to Jerusalem. ¹⁶ They will be brought in joy and praise and they will enter the temple of the king of ages. ¹⁷ In the place of your fathers will be the righteous, your sons; you will appoint them as leaders in all the land. ¹⁸ At that time you will say, "We will invoke your name in every generation"; because of this the Gentiles who are converted will praise your name forever and ever and ever.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction & Superscript

This Psalm is seen as a song of praise for the Sages of the Sanhedrin of Moses and was composed prophetically by the sons of Korach. This explanation comes from the Targum. The Sages are the interpreters of the Torah who lived in the latter years before Yeshua and for a few years after. Korach was the person who led a failed rebellion against Moses (can be found in Numbers 16:2). The sons of Korach at first helped their father but later on decided that their father was wrong. The sons turned on their father and supported Moses.

The Torah scholar resembles a rose. This is a delicate flower surrounded by thorns. The thorns seem ready to pierce the flower's delicate petals. But instead, the thorns protect the petals.

The Midrash for this Psalm equates it to Abraham, David, and the Messiah. Each was first rejected by people and later accepted.

Rabbi Hirsch explains the Psalm as a wedding song celebrating the marriage of a bride and groom. Arranged marriages bring together two people who do not know each other well. Conflicts occur at the beginning of the marriage as the couple learns about each other. Eventually, they learn to love each other. Hirsch's explanation fits the ideas of the Midrash. Abraham was chastised for spreading his belief in a single all-powerful

God. Still, he was eventually accepted, and his people became the Jewish nation. David was vilified and pursued by Saul. After a civil war, David became the most beloved King of Israel. The Midrash says that the Messiah will arrive and be challenged before acceptance.

The Psalmist calls out to the Sefirah Netzach for victory.

To Him who grants victory, upon the roses, by the sons of Korach, an instruction, a song of friendship.

Verse one

Ordinary writers search for pretty words that would express an emotion. The Korachite's source was not in their heads but rather in their hearts. Thus this song was fully formed within the author's heart. The words serve only to utter that which the heart has created. The tongue is merely the stenographer's pen which allows the notes of the song to be written down.

My heart has given me this song which I now utter to a king; my tongue will utter the words so the pen can write them down.

Verse two

People can see that you are not ordinary. The LORD has appointed you to such a high calling. The Psalmist does not glorify the royal crown. He glorifies the attributes that are a part of a king's personality and would distinguish him from other men even if he were not a king.

You are fairer than ordinary men; grace is poured upon your lips; therefore, God has blessed you forever.

Verse three

The sword at your side is not for decoration. It symbolizes your majesty because you wield it as a hero.

Gird your sword around your thigh, O mighty one; it is your majesty and ornament.

Verse four

This person employs the service of the cause of truth and right in their life.

But this is your true glory; process and wield guidance for the cause of truth and the championless right; then your right hand will teach you amazing things.

Verse five

The preceding verses describe the usage of royal power in peacetime. When this is done for the service of truth, the arrows become the weapon of victory against the king's enemies.

Your arrows are sharp; The people fall under you; Those who are the king's foes have the arrows piercing their hearts.

Verse six

This verse recognizes that the LORD is the ruler of the Earth forever.

Your throne, God is forever and ever because the scepter of equity is the scepter of your kingdom.

Verse seven

What makes the LORD different from the false gods and idols is that the LORD loves righteousness and hates evil. Evil must be eliminated because it is an obstacle to the exercise and cultivation of all that is good.

You love righteousness by hating lawlessness; therefore, God, your God, has anointed you with gladsome consecration above your fellows.

Verse eight

The fragrances on the garments can be smelt. The odor comes from the fragrant trees making the king glad.

With myrrh and aloes, and cassia are all in your garments, from the ivory palaces (towers) which gladdened you.

Verse nine

The king's daughters are present to participate in the wedding feast.

King's daughters are among Your noble ladies; at your right-hand stands the queen in gold jewelry of Ophir.

Verse ten

The Psalmist tells the ladies to give their attention to what they see and hear. They are to dismiss from their mind any thoughts that make them sad.

Hearken, O daughter and see, incline your ear and forget your own kinfolk and your father's house.

Verse eleven

The Psalmist tells the ladies not to grieve because sadness can affect their beauty.

So that the king shall rejoice in your beauty, for he is your master, and bow down to him.

Verse twelve

A delegation from Tyre will come to pay homage to the ladies.

The daughter of Tyre will come with a gift; the rich among the people will seek your favor.

Verse thirteen

The princess may appear glorious and splendid in public. She only reveals her true glory in womanly virtue in a quiet, more private circle. Her inner beauty outshines her outer beauty.

But the King's daughter is all glorious within, more than in the golden borders of her attire.

Verse fourteen

She comes before the king in the most beautiful clothing.

She is brought to embroideries only for the sake of the king; the maidens who attend her are her friends. They are led to you.

Verse fifteen

They are led with gladness and rejoicing; they enter the palace of the king.

Verse sixteen

The joy of being a parent is that one of the daughters' sons will become king.

May your sons step into the palace of your fathers; may you appoint them as princes in all the lands.

Verse seventeen

I will cause your name to be remembered in all generations; therefore, the people will give you thanks forever and ever.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Him who grants victory, upon the roses, by the sons of Korach, an instruction, a song of friendship.

My heart has given me this song which I now utter to a king; my tongue will utter the words so the pen can write them down.

You are fairer than ordinary men; grace is poured upon your lips; therefore, God has blessed you forever.

Gird your sword around your thigh, O mighty one; it is your majesty and ornament.

But this is your true glory; process and wield guidance for the cause of truth and the championless right; then your right hand will teach you amazing things.

Your arrows are sharp; The people fall under you; Those who are the king's foes have the arrows piercing their hearts.

Your throne, God is forever and ever because the scepter of equity is the scepter of your kingdom.

You love righteousness by hating lawlessness; therefore, God, your God, has anointed you with gladsome consecration above your fellows.

With myrrh and aloes, and cassia are all in your garments, from the ivory palaces (towers) which gladdened you.

King's daughters are among Your noble ladies; at your right-hand stands the queen in gold jewelry of Ophir.

Hearken, O daughter and see, incline your ear and forget your own kinfolk and your father's house.

So that the king shall rejoice in your beauty, for he is your master, and bow down to him.

The daughter of Tyre will come with a gift; the rich among the people will seek your favor.

The daughter of Tyre will come with a gift; the rich among the people will seek your favor.

But the King's daughter is all glorious within, more than in the golden borders of her attire.

She is brought to embroideries only for the sake of the king; the maidens who attend her are her friends. They are led to you.

They are led with gladness and rejoicing; they enter the palace of the king.

May your sons step into the palace of your fathers; may you appoint them as princes in all the lands.

I will cause your name to be remembered in all generations; therefore, the people will give you thanks forever and ever.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

